

The social and economic impact of COVID-19 on SRH, TB and HIV prevention and treatment access, well-being, and economic vulnerability of adolescent girls and women living with or at risk for HIV in Africa

Research Proposal

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Abstract

Background The COVID-19 pandemic is deepening pre-existing inequalities and discriminations, exposing vulnerabilities in social, political, and economic systems, which are in turn amplifying the impacts of the pandemic. Emerging evidence suggests that women's economic and productive lives will be affected disproportionately. Additionally, adolescent girls and women may find it more difficult to access health services due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Recovery measures must address public health gaps, design fiscal stimulus packages and social assistance programmes to achieve greater equity, opportunities, and social protection of women and girls, including those living with HIV, which is vital in the context of the pandemic. Thus, the impact of COVID-19 on HIV and TB prevention and treatment access, well-being and economic vulnerability among adolescent girls and women living with or at risk of HIV must be assessed.

Objective This research project is aimed at conducting an observational, non-interventional, global cross-sectional internet survey to determine how the COVID-19 crisis has exacerbated economic vulnerabilities and inequalities among adolescent girls and women living with or at risk of HIV. Additionally, this study aims to determine the sociodemographic, economic, and clinical factors associated with reduced access to SRH, TB, and HIV prevention and treatment following the COVID-19 crisis among participants.

Methods An internet sampling method will be used to conduct the cross-sectional survey recruiting adolescent girls and women living with or at risk of HIV in South Africa, Egypt, Nigeria, Zimbabwe, and Senegal. Internet sampling has proven capable of reaching hard-to-sample populations, increasing the number of respondents from hard-to-reach populations, quickening recruitment, lowering operational costs, and increasing anonymity and security provided to participants. To safeguard the data privacy, rights, and welfare of the research participants, access to the online survey will be provided via anonymous weblink. The survey will be open for six (6) weeks. The cross-sectional study is observational by nature and does not alter the exposure status of respondents and thus warrants minimal to no risk for the participants. We will perform analyses to characterize the impact of COVID-19 on economic, social, mental, and physical health, as well as SRH, TB, and HIV prevention and care among the survey participants. The survey questionnaire provides essential components to fulfill the study objectives and was developed using selected standard protocols.

Key words COVID-19, gender discrimination, stigma, HIV, TB, SRH, Africa, internet survey

Research Protocol

Introduction

Background

The COVID-19 pandemic poses serious threats to physical and mental health, as well as economic stability, across the globe. As of August 26, 2020, there were over 1.2 million confirmed cases and more than 28 thousand deaths in Africa [1]. Five countries are home to 63% of COVID-19 cases: South Africa (34%) Egypt (16%) Nigeria (6%), Ghana (4%) and Cameroon (3%) [1]. Efforts to curb the spread of COVID-19 have slowed the growth of new cases but have also led to unprecedented disruptions, with far-reaching health care, social, and economic consequences. The pandemic is deepening pre-existing inequalities and discriminations, exposing vulnerabilities in social, political, and economic systems which are in turn amplifying the impacts of the pandemic.

Emerging evidence on the impact of COVID-19 suggests that women's economic and productive lives will be affected differently and disproportionately from men [2]. They have less access to social protections and are more likely to bear the demand of supporting single-parent households [2]. Their capacity to absorb economic shocks is therefore less than that of men. As women take on greater care demands at home, their jobs will also be disproportionately affected by cuts and lay-offs [2]. The situation is worse in developing economies where most of the women's employment is in the informal economy, which offers few protections against dismissal or for paid sick leave and provides limited access to social protection [2]. In sub-Saharan Africa, 74 percent of women in non-agricultural jobs are in informal employment [3]. In Nigeria, this figure is 90 percent [4].

As the COVID-19 pandemic is coupled with restricted movement and social isolation measures, gender-based violence is increasing [5]. Many African women were or still are in 'lockdown' at home with their abusers while being cut off from normal support services [6]. In Nigeria, sexual and gender-based violence increased by 256% in two weeks of lockdown [7]. It is expected that an additional 2 million instances of intimate partner violence can be expected in 2020-2021 as a result of COVID-19 [8]. In Kenya, calls for help against domestic violence increased by 34 percent in the first three weeks of the curfew [9]. These impacts are further amplified in contexts of fragility, conflict, and emergencies where social cohesion is already undermined and institutional capacity and services are limited.

Rationale for research

Health pandemics can make it more difficult for women and girls to receive treatment and health services [10]. This is compounded by multiple or intersecting inequalities, such as ethnicity, socioeconomic status, disability, age, race, geographic location, and sexual orientation, among others which influences access and decision-making to critical health services. Women and girls have unique health needs, but they are less likely to have access to quality health services, essential medicines and vaccines, maternal and reproductive health care, or insurance coverage for routine and catastrophic health costs, especially in rural and marginalized communities. The provision of sexual and reproductive health services, including maternal health care and gender-

based violence related services, are central to health, rights and well-being of women and girls. The diversion of attention and critical resources away from these provisions may result in exacerbated maternal mortality and morbidity, increased rates of adolescent pregnancies, HIV, and sexually transmitted diseases.

HIV treatment access needs to be maintained with no interruptions, particularly, but not exclusively in terms of prevention of mother to child transmission of HIV. COVID-19 may amplify existing barriers to HIV prevention, testing, treatment, and care [11,12]. HIV treatment interruptions can lead to 1) increased HIV viral load, lower CD4 count, HIV disease progression, and increased risk of developing an opportunistic infection; 2) side effects, or difficulties with adherence upon restarting HIV treatment; 3) drug resistance; and 4) unsuppressed viral load that can also contribute to increased risk of HIV transmission. It is therefore critical to assess how COVID-19 has impacted access to HIV prevention and testing, and HIV treatment and care services. A modelling group convened by the WHO and UNAIDS has estimated that if efforts are not made to mitigate and overcome interruptions in health services and supplies during the COVID-19 pandemic, a six-month disruption of antiretroviral therapy could lead to more than 500 000 extra deaths from AIDS-related illnesses, including from tuberculosis, in sub-Saharan Africa in 2020–2021 [12].

COVID-19 recovery measures must address public health gaps, design fiscal stimulus packages and social assistance programmes to achieve greater equity, opportunities, and social protection of women and girls, including those living with HIV, which is vital in the context of the pandemic. This includes gender-responsive economic and social policies and placing women's economic lives at the heart of the pandemic response and recovery plans. There is need to measure the impact of COVID-19 on HIV and TB prevention and treatment access, well-being and economic vulnerability of adolescent girls and young women living with or at risk of HIV.

Methods and Design

a) Scientific design of the study

The survey objectives

This research project is aimed to:

- Determine the consequences in terms of economic vulnerabilities and increased inequalities of the COVID-19 crisis among adolescent girls and women living with or at-risk of HIV;
- Determine the sociodemographic, economic, and clinical factors associated with the reduced access to SRH, TB, and HIV prevention and treatment among adolescent girls and women during and following the COVID-19 crisis.

Methods

Investigators

The research project involves the Strategic Information Department (SID) at the Joint United Nations Programmes on HIV/AIDS (UNAIDS).

Scientific peer review

The research proposal has been reviewed and accepted by a scientific peer review group independent from the research project team. The comments from the scientific review group have been incorporated into the final proposal (Appendix 1).

The reviewers are (alphabetical order):

- Sean Howell (The LGBT Foundation)
- Ehimario Igumbor (Nigerian Centre for Disease Control, Abuja, Nigeria, University of Western Cape)
- Warraisha Abdool Karim (Caprisa, University of KwaZulu Natal)
- Morenike Oluwatoyin Ukpong (Obafemi Awolowo University)
- Bruno Ventelou (CNRS, University of Aix-Marseille)

Target population support for the survey

We engaged with members of the target population to seek their input on survey content to ensure that the survey design is consistent with on-the-ground realities and to further encourage target population participation. In addition, we made sure to involve representatives of the different communities in the core team of the survey, including young women, women living with HIV, LGBT+, and sex workers. The in-country research team will be deliberately designed to include female-identifying research trainees (postgraduate students) and under-represented sociodemographic groups.

Ethical consideration

The study protocol will be submitted to the national board of ethics in each country as required. It is also being provided for review to the WHO Research Ethics Review Committee (ERC).

Funding

The total budget is USD 162 500, and the UNAIDS requested budget for this research study is USD 85 000. This requested budget will cover the first round of the survey in all five countries. Additional financing is being sought out for conducting a second round in 2021. A budget is attached (Appendix 2).

Timing and intervals between the survey rounds

A first round will be rolled out during Q4 (2020) and will provide UNAIDS and partners a clear picture of the socioeconomic and health impact of the COVID-19 crisis on the different groups of African adolescent girls and women covered in this survey. A second round is planned for Q2 (2021), subject to financing. The second round will provide updated information and elucidate any trends following the COVID-19 crisis. A detailed timeline is attached (Appendix 3).

Questionnaire development

The questionnaire of the survey contains established instruments for collecting survey data among key populations, including adolescent girls and young women living with HIV/AIDS and at risk for HIV, using validated questions and scores. These instruments include questions that have been used throughout the world; thus, their continued use will enable researchers to compare survey results across countries. The standardized instruments provided with these guidelines were designed to be self-administered using electronic or web-based data collection methods.

The questionnaire was built on the following four principles:

1. The privacy and security of respondents must be ensured at every step of the survey;
2. Questionnaire should be as short as possible. Only questions that are necessary should be included;
3. Filling out the online questionnaire should expose participants to no more than minimal risk, such as minimal discomfort, minimal anxiety;
4. Questions selected should have their reliability and validity already demonstrated and their collection should enable triangulation with other surveys.

We followed the following key steps in questionnaire development:

- deciding on methods for questionnaire administration;
- determining investigation topics (questionnaire domains);
- developing and adapting the questionnaire;
- conducting cognitive testing;
- pre-testing the questionnaire;
- pilot testing the survey tool.

The content of the questionnaire is harmonized with standard indicators and protocol checklists used in behavioural surveillance. The questionnaire is organised as modules focused on topics, such as:

- Sociodemographics
 - Age
 - Country of residence
 - Sex assigned at birth, gender identity, and sexual orientation
 - Racial/ethnic group
 - Immigrant status
- History of sex work
- TB or HIV serostatus
- The impacts of COVID-19 on the following areas:
 - HIV prevention, testing, treatment, and care
 - Access to TB and SRH services
 - Mental health
 - Vulnerability and violence
 - Substance use
 - Economics and behavioural economics

Languages and translations

The survey will be made available in English, Arabic, and French, as well as dominant national languages, including Zulu, Afrikaans, Xhosa, Sesotho sa Leboa, Setswana, Pidgin, Hausa, Igbo, Yoruba, Shona, Ndebele, Wolof, and Bambara.

Translations are performed from the original English version at the country level by native speakers with the appropriate technical knowledge. Translated documents are retranslated to English by a second translator and discrepancies are discussed with the research team and adjusted accordingly. Piloting each language version allows users to provide feedback on translations, which is used to adjust the meaning and connotation of each language version to match the English version and intended meaning as closely as possible.

Data management

For cost efficiency, participant's answers will be uploaded using an online survey tool such as LimeSurvey. Different completion modalities will be offered. This includes through participants' own devices, with airtime vouchers provided by country research partners and financed with the budget of this proposal. For hard-to-reach participants, participants without internet-capable devices (e.g. smartphone), or participants with reading impairment, interviewers will offer to fill the form based on the responses provided by the interviewees, or can provide the latter with a device to fill the survey on the spot. Finally, interviewers may also use paper copy and upload the responses online once back to the office. For all cases, informed consent will be required, and members of the research team will sign a declaration of confidentiality and privacy. All data will be irrevocably anonymised and paper copies will be destroyed.

Data analysis, use, and dissemination

We selected internet sampling for it demonstrated higher number of respondents among hard-to-reach populations, faster recruitment, lower operational cost, greater level of anonymity provided to participants. Acknowledging selection bias, we may apply techniques, e.g. prediction modelling, to correct for the bias that results from differential access to, and use of, the internet. See also section (p) limitations below.

We will perform descriptive analyses to characterise the impact of COVID-19 and the economic slowdown that will follow, on economic, social, mental and physical health, SRH, TB and HIV prevention and care on survey participants. Outcomes will be stratified by key sociodemographic and clinical characteristics, including HIV status, being a racial/ethnic minority, immigrant status, health insurance coverage, and engaging in transactional sex and/or in sex work. We will examine between-group differences using Fisher's Exact and Chi-Squared tests, as appropriate, with a significance level of $\alpha=0.05$.

Data collected during the survey are anonymised and will be managed in a way that protects the privacy of participants and the confidentiality of the information they provided. We will take measures to prevent the unintended collection of IP addresses.

Data will be owned by UNAIDS. Data will be stored by UNAIDS in their on-premise file storage, protected with always-on real-time firewall and antivirus. Access to the anonymised individual data folder will be password protected and restricted to authorised users, after completion of a Declaration of Confidentiality and Data Privacy. Data are not and will not be

monetised. Any data shared outside the survey team – such as with a third party conducting secondary analysis – will be anonymized. When disseminating results, the data will be aggregated at a higher level to ensure that the information does not enable to suspect or reveal the identity of any individual participant or group of participants.

Country analysis

Additional questions may be looked at following this first phase and might include country-specific questions in order to increase the relevance of HIV prevention, care and treatment interventions, zero discrimination interventions and advocacy, or human rights interventions, among others. The intent of this study is to focus first on the five African countries included in the survey, but pending the results of this research, it may be extended to other regions.

Feedbacks of results to communities

To ensure that survey data reaches a diverse range of stakeholders including participants, community-based and advocacy organizations, policy-makers, researchers, HIV and public health funders, and the international community, the dissemination process will be informed by a research utilisation framework ensuring that iterative, digestible indicators such as policy briefs, advocacy briefs; infographics and downloadable slide sets, as well as abstracts and presentations at conferences, will be made available. Relevant target conferences for data dissemination include IAS 2021, European AIDS Conference, HIVNAT, and others.

b) Relevance of the research to the health needs of the target population

It is critical to consider both the direct and indirect health impacts of the crisis on women and girls, including transgender women and those involved in transactional sex or in sex work. This research study aims to explore how women and girls' lives are changing in the face of COVID-19, including social and economic impact, access to health, including sexual and reproductive health services, maternal health care and gender-based violence related services, HIV, to inform priority measures to mitigate the impact and to strengthen access to health services, including HIV, sexual and reproductive health/rights. While a few other COVID related surveys are being rolled out, this is to our knowledge the first survey aimed at assessing the impact of COVID and socio-economic consequences on young women and girls living with HIV and at risk for HIV.

c) Sampling strategy, recruitment and voluntary informed consent

Participants will be recruited through a combined approach of i) online survey ii) social networking, including youth and women's organizations, CSOs and women's rights organizations, religious and traditional leaders, volunteer groups, and networks of people living with HIV and sex workers networks and transgender networks where it exists; and iii) through data collection interviewers for hard-to-reach group.

Participation in the survey will be voluntary and following provision of written informed consent. Responses will be anonymised and no personal or identifiable information will be collected.

d) Justification of the research design

(to be completed)

e) Gender considerations relevant to the project

The online survey focuses on adolescent girls and young women living with or at risk of HIV with a focus on those living with disabilities, those involved in transactional sex or sex work, migrants, refugees, and transgender women.

The survey was provided for review to the members of the target population. Their feedback and comments were considered and analysed at various stages of proposal development. The comments were considered and incorporated into the final version of the questionnaire.

f) The benefits that the research will likely produce

The main benefit of the online survey is to inform the impact of COVID-19 and how sociodemographic, economic, and clinical factors worsen access to SRH, TB, and HIV prevention and treatment among adolescent girls and women in South Africa, Egypt, Nigeria, Zimbabwe, and Senegal.

The analysis that will follow will support advocacy and better programme design for adolescent girls and women in low- and middle-income countries.

g) A description of physical, social, psychological, and economic risks to both individuals and communities

The safety and data security of the target population is a top priority in planning and implementation of our survey. We learned from the experience of the previous web-based and consulted with the target population. The survey will be conducted anonymously, meaning that personal identifiers will not be recorded on any forms. Unique survey codes will be used in all records and constructed without the use of personal identifying information such as any identifiable numbers.

By design this survey is a cross-sectional survey, where the investigators will measure the outcome and the exposures not altering the exposure status.

The survey instruments were previously administrated in communities and proved minimal to no psychological risk for the respondents. We still acknowledge that some sensitive personal questions may trigger anxiety in some respondents.

However, we anticipate minimal to no risk for the study participants. To monitor any related cases, we created a mailbox to respond quickly and appropriately on any query and/or event related to this survey.

h) Vulnerability to harm or to risk of exploitation

It does not collect any personal information and records are unidentifiable. The questions, taken all together, do not reveal any information that could make respondents vulnerable to harm or to risk of exploitation. The questionnaire does not use or collect geolocation data, it does not install

any tracker cookies on the device of the respondents. We anticipate no harm or risk of exploitation.

i) Steps that will be taken to minimize the risks to participants, including confidentiality and privacy

As described in the section above, the online questionnaire should not entail no more than minimal risk in terms of potential stress and/or anxiety while responding to the questionnaire. The online questionnaire compiles questions previously used in other surveys and, to the best of our knowledge, do not have any physical risk.

The data privacy and protection of information obtained from participants is important for this survey. To protect the anonymity and data privacy of the participants, the following steps have been taken:

- The study is made available to the target population through a secure, SSL encrypted connection link
- The link does not require any personal identifier, email, phone or person-to-person contact
- Data in transit (ex: while responding online) are encrypted using secure TLS cryptographic protocols
- The collection tool, LimeSurvey, has certified its compliance with the EU-U.S. Privacy Shield Framework (GDPR) and Swiss-U.S. Privacy Shield
- The questionnaire does not collect any personal information. Questions, even taken all together, do not reveal any information that could enable identification of respondents or their geolocation
- The collection tool does not install any targeting or advertising cookies
- IP addresses are instantly decoupled from the questionnaire, encrypted, and deleted at the end of the online survey (6 weeks) by the survey tool
- Data records are unidentifiable

We have, to the best of our knowledge, taken all the measures to prevent any identification of the respondents by the research team as well as by any authority.

We believe we have taken all the necessary steps to ensure data privacy and to protect the confidentiality of information obtained from participants, and to protect them from social or economic discrimination or stigmatization following their participation to the online questionnaire.

Furthermore, as mentioned above, a mailbox representing the participating agencies will be provided to address any query and/or event related to this survey.

j) Adverse events

Building on earlier experiences of non-medical internet surveys, the risk of adverse or serious adverse events is considered unlikely and minimal. We are taking considerate steps to safeguard confidentiality for the consenting research participants and data privacy. We anticipate that the risks to the research participants are minimal in relation to potential benefits for the target population. We will provide adequate provision for oversight and monitoring the safety and data. Also, as mentioned above, we guarantee engagement and will create a mailbox representing the

participating agencies to address any query and/or event related to this survey. As such we are aimed to ensure follow up care for participants with any query and/or event related to this survey.

k) Details on how the study will be monitored

The survey will be available for completion online for 6 weeks. The research team will monitor the situation of the online questionnaire as well as the response rate per country. Country-level websites will be used to post reminders periodically to boost participation.

The mail address for requesting information and right of withdrawal will be open for the full duration of the survey. This mail address will be administered by staff from UNAIDS. This staff will not be involved in the survey itself and will have signed the Declaration of Confidentiality and Data Privacy.

l) Sample size

With respect to budget constraints, we aim to reach 380 participants for each of the six subpopulation groups, corresponding to 2,280 participants per country. Where data on the population size of different groups exist, we will aim to reach a sample size that enables statistical regressions with 95% confidence level and 5% margin of error (confidence interval). For example, for 4.93 million women living with HIV in South Africa, the theoretical sample size would be 385 respondents. Similarly, sex workers population in South Africa and Nigeria is estimated to 24,000 and 103,000 respectively. Ideal sample sizes we would try to reach would then be 379 and 383 respondents, respectively. For multilevel multiple regression analysis, anticipating up to five predictor variables for the level 1 (e.g. individual level) and three predictor variables for the level 2 (e.g. country level data), a minimum sample size of 81 is required for 0.05 p-value regressions.

The online questionnaire is built in two modules: a sociodemographic module and a module on HIV stigma. Respondents must complete a module and click on 'next' in order to have their responses recorded. Any respondent leaving the survey before completing a module is de facto excluded from the survey. Respondents choosing to click on the 'exit' button are also excluded from the survey.

To increase the quality of the dataset, the research team will construct discrepancy flags which indicate whether respondents supplied inconsistent data in different areas of the questionnaire.

Non-qualifiers are respondents who did not meet the criteria for inclusion in the study. Non-qualifying cases include:

- Consent not provided
- Not providing a numeric value for age
- Not belonging to any of the study target populations

m) Compensation of immediate medical or other assistance

This research is non-medical by nature and any medical or other assistance is unlikely. However, we guarantee engagement and will create a mailbox representing the participating agencies to address any query and/or event related to this survey.

n) Incentives offered to participants

The survey team will provide airtime vouchers to participants because of the data/internet usage expense for those who complete the online survey on their own device.

o) Any information that will be provided to participants following their participation

The following elements are presented to respondents upon completion of the survey:

- A message thanking them for their participation in the survey and a reminder of the anonymity of the survey;
- A weblink for additional information on the survey, periodical updates, and general findings and next steps;
- An advocacy message encouraging participants to get tested for HIV infection.

Due to the anonymity given to participants and the IP addresses being decoupled and encrypted automatically during the time that the survey is online (6 weeks), there is no possibility to provide further direct information to participants after completion of the questionnaire.

p) Limitations of the survey

Although the combination of recruitment approaches and survey format will encourage optimal coverage of the various target populations, there remain limitations that must be acknowledged. As for any survey using a convenience sample, selection bias is present (not all subpopulation groups may be represented proportionately), and the survey is not meant to be formally generalisable to the entire female population of the selected countries or of subpopulation groups.

Additionally, internet access remains a barrier for many within the target population. Individuals in the target population may face financial or material constraints to access the internet and thus the survey. Country partners will supply airtime vouchers to participants to mitigate this barrier. The study team will also go into the community and engage directly with the target population to provide alternative methods for completing the survey. However, it must be acknowledged that those who are not in direct contact with the study team may not be able to participate in the survey due to these barriers. This may lead to members of the target population not being represented.

Finally, possible variations may exist between languages. When available, we used validated translations of questions. When translations were not available, the study team made sure that the translations were as similar in meaning and connotation as possible from the original English version. This was achieved by performing translation and retranslation to English as proofreading at the country level as well as testing the language among users. Despite these efforts, the specificities of the different languages make it nearly impossible to ensure exact correspondence.

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Appendix 1: Online Questionnaire

Survey on the impact of COVID-19 on HIV services, wellbeing, and economic vulnerability of women and girls living with or at risk for HIV in South Africa

Dear Participant,

Thank you for participating in this survey which will help improve actions taken in response to the COVID-19 pandemic and inform the response to similar future outbreaks. **The purpose of this survey is to understand and explore the various impacts of the COVID-19 crisis on the health and wellbeing of women and girls living with or at risk for HIV in South Africa, as well as related economic shocks as a driver of heightened vulnerability of women and girls.**

This study will involve completing a 20-minute survey that will ask you questions relating to the coronavirus.

Participation is open to woman and girls aged at least 15-year-old, living in South Africa and is voluntary. This survey is anonymous. Please be reassured, that all responses are confidential. You can skip questions you are not comfortable with. You can also stop participating in the survey at any moment by closing the page.

This study is conducted by CAPRISA in collaboration with UNAIDS, AIDS Foundation of South Africa (AFSA), African Alliance and Youth Health Africa the Institute of Public Health. It has been approved by the University of KwaZulu-Natal Ethics Committee (BREC/00002727/2021).

By taking part, you are agreeing that you have read and understood the information about the

study provided below. Please click on "show policy" below for more details about the study, and contact details of the research group.

There are 145 questions in this survey.

Socio-demographic background

Please tell us a bit about you and your background.

All your answers are confidential and nobody can identify you. It is anonymous.

1 Data Collector's Identification (skip if you answer this survey by yourself)

Please write your answer here:

2 In which province do you currently live?*

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Eastern Cape
- Free State
- Gauteng
- KwaZulu-Natal
- Limpopo
- Mpumalanga
- Northern Cape
- North West
- Western Cape

3 How old are you?* *

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Under 15
- 15-18
- 19-24
- 25-30
- 31-34
- 35-39
- 40-44
- 45-49
- 50-54
- 55-59
- 60-64
- 65 +

4 Can you confirm your race?

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- African / Black
- Coloured
- Asian / Indian
- White
- I cannot or do not wish to answer
- I don't know
- Other

5 What is your religion?

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Catholic
- Hinduism
- Islam
- Judaism
- Protestant
- Traditional
- None
- I prefer not to answer
- Other

6 Do you identify having a disability (do you have a physical or mental condition that limits your movements, senses, or daily activities)?

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No
- I cannot or do not wish to answer this question
- I don't know

7 Do you have difficulty in the following domains?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' or 'I don't know' at question '6 [Q6]' (Do you identify having a disability (do you have a physical or mental condition that limits your movements, senses, or daily activities)?)

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	No difficulty	Some difficulty	A lot of difficulty	Cannot function at all
Seeing even if wearing glasses	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Hearing even if using a hearing aid	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Walking or climbing steps	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Remembering or concentrating	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Speech (like using your usual language)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Personal care (like washing all over or dressing)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

8 What is your highest level of schooling completed?

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- No formal education
- Quranic only
- Primary school
- High school or secondary school
- Trade school, vocational training, or apprenticeship
- Postsecondary education or some college
- University

9 What type of dwelling or house do you live in?

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- A house or a flat
- A traditional house like a mud hut
- An informal house like a shack
- A refugee camp / temporary shelter
- A women's shelter
- Rehabilitation centre
- I have no place to live in

Other

10 In your household, is there:

❗ Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Electricity
- A mobile phone
- A television
- A gas or electric stove
- A refrigerator
- A computer
- Internet at home
- A bicycle
- A motorcycle
- A car
- Do not own any of the items on this list

11 What is the main source of drinking water for members of your household?

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Piped water into dwelling
- Piped water into yard
- Piped to neighbour
- Public tap / standpipe
- Tube well or borehole
- Dug well, unprotected
- Dug well, protected (wellhead is protected by a plastered cement slab)
- Water from spring
- Rainwater
- Tanker truck
- Cart with small tank
- Surface water (river, dam, lake, canal, ...)
- Bottled water
- Other

12 What kind of toilet facility do members of your household usually use?

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Flush toilet
- Pit latrine with slab
- Pit latrine without slab / open pit
- No facility / bush /field

13 Does any members of this household own any agricultural land?

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

14 Which of the following describes the place where you currently live?

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- A large city
- A town
- A village
- A farm or isolated house

15 In this city, you live in:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'A large city' or 'A town' at question '14 [Q14]' (Which of the following describes the place where you currently live?)

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- A wealthy suburb
- A middle-class suburb
- A poor suburb
- A township
- A refugee camp / temporary shelter
- I cannot or do not wish to answer this question

16 Indicate the total number of people living with you in your household? (you included)

● Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- 1 (only me)
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- 10
- 11
- 12
- 13
- 14
- 15 and more

17 With whom do you currently live?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was NOT '1 (only me)' at question '16 [Q16]' (Indicate the total number of people living with you in your household? (you included))

❗ Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Alone, no other person
- Spouse
- A sexual or romantic partner (non-spouse)
- Other adult family members
- Close friend(s) or roommate(s)
- Children under the age of 18
- Children above the age of 18
- Any other adult (not close friend)
- Other

18 What is your current relationship status?

❗ Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Single
- Married
- In a relationship but not living together
- In more than one relationship
- Divorced / separated
- Widowed
- Other
- I cannot or do not wish to answer this question

19 How many children do you have?

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- 0
- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- 10 or more

20 Do you have young children (under 18y)?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was NOT '0' at question '19 [Q19]' (How many children do you have?)

❗ Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Yes, living with me
- Yes, but not living with me
- No, my children are above 18
- I don't know
- I cannot or do not wish to answer this question

21 Who do you have sex with?

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Men only
- Women only
- Both men and women
- Other (example: asexual, pansexual, ...)
- I have never had sex
- I don't know
- I cannot or do not wish to answer this question

22 How would you primarily define your gender identity?

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Woman
- Transgender woman (male to female)
- Transgender man (female to male)
- I don't know
- I cannot or do not wish to answer this question
- Other

23 What sex were you assigned at birth?

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Female
- Male
- Intersex - my sex was unclear at birth and/or I was diagnosed with an intersex condition

The COVID-19 epidemic

This section contains questions on the health and non-health impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on you.

24 In general, how would you rate your health?

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Excellent
- Very good
- Good
- Fair
- Poor

25 Do you use public transport?

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes, more than before the COVID-19 crisis
- Yes, same as before the COVID-19 crisis
- Yes, less than before the COVID-19 crisis
- Not anymore since COVID-19 crisis
- No, never

26 Have you or anyone in your household been screened or tested for COVID-19 ?

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

27 Have you or anyone in your household ever had a positive COVID-19 test result?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '26 [Q26]' (Have you or anyone in your household been screened or tested for COVID-19 ?)

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

28 What precautions do you take to avoid becoming infected or reinfected with COVID-19?

🗖️ Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- No particular measure
- Wash or sanitize my hands frequently
- Wearing a re-usable cloth or disposable face mask
- Avoid crowded areas
- Avoid going out
- Daily monitoring of signs and symptoms
- Going to a health facility or testing site for a COVID-19 test if I have signs or symptoms
- Getting vaccinated

29 What challenge do you face in taking measures to prevent COVID-19 infection?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was at question '28 [Q28]' (What precautions do you take to avoid becoming infected or reinfected with COVID-19?)

🗖️ Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- There is no place to wash my hands around where I live
- I cannot afford to pay for cloth or disposable face masks
- I cannot afford to buy soap or sanitizers
- I cannot avoid crowded areas
- I already had COVID-19
- I don't really care about COVID-19
- There is no COVID-19 here
- Other

30 Are you worried that you or someone in your immediate family may become seriously ill from COVID-19?

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

A1

Very worried

A2

Somewhat worried

A3

Not too worried

A0

Not worried at all

31 What makes you confident that you or your relative will not become seriously ill from COVID-19?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Not worried at all' or 'Not too worried' at question '30 [Q30]' (Are you worried that you or someone in your immediate family may become seriously ill from COVID-19?)

🗳️ Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

I follow preventive measures (handwashing, physical distancing, masks, etc.)

We are strong and healthy

Weather is hot here

God will protect us

It is curable/treatable

There is no COVID-19 here

Other:

32 When a vaccine for COVID-19 is available to me, I will get it

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

A4

A3

A2

A1

33 What are the reasons you are not sure you want a vaccine for COVID-19?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Strongly disagree' or 'Disagree' at question '32 [Q32]' (When a vaccine for COVID-19 is available to me, I will get it)

🗳️ Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- I think the risk to me of getting COVID-19 is low
- I'm against vaccines in general
- It is not a priority for me
- I am afraid of side effects
- My family or the person I live with (husband, partner, etc) is against it
- Registering for it could put me in trouble due to my situation (example I'm an illegal worker, migrant, etc)
- I think it is against my religion
- I do not trust what the authorities say
- I do not have time to go to a health centre for a vaccine
-
- Other:

34 Did you have to stop school/ university/ college due to the COVID-19 pandemic?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was '25-30' or '19-24' or '15-18' at question '3 [Q3]' (How old are you?*)

📌 Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No
- Does not apply to me

35 What made you stop school during COVID-19 pandemic?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '34 [Q34]' (Did you have to stop school/ university/ college due to the COVID-19 pandemic?)

📌 Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- The school/ university/ college was closed due to the COVID-19
- My parents or my family did not allow this
- Nobody to look after my child/children
- Money problems
- Stigma
- I had no data /internet to attend online classes
- I became pregnant
- I don't know
- Other

36 Are you planning to return to school after the pandemic?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '34 [Q34]' (Did you have to stop school/ university/ college due to the COVID-19 pandemic?)

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes, I have already returned to school
- Yes, later
- No
- I don't know / I am not sure

Your economic and social situation

This page includes questions on work, income, benefits, and how COVID-19 crisis affected your socio-economic situation.

37 How many people contribute financially to your household (you included)?

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- 10 and more

38

In the last 30 days, did you do any work, do any kind of business, farming, or other activity in exchange of a salary, cash or in kind, even if only for few hours?

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

Yes

No

39 Are you paid in cash or in-kind for this work or are you not paid at all?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '38 [Q38]' (In the last 30 days, did you do any work, do any kind of business, farming, or other activity in exchange of a salary, cash or in kind, even if only for few hours?)

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

Cash only

Cash and kind

In kind only

Not paid

40 What is the main reason you are not currently working?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No' at question '38 [Q38]' (In the last 30 days, did you do any work, do any kind of business, farming, or other activity in exchange of a salary, cash or in kind, even if only for few hours?)

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Business or office closed due to Covid legal restrictions
- Business or office closed for another reason
- I was retrenched or lost my job
- I have been temporarily told not to work
- I am ill or quarantined
- I need to care for the children while schools are closed
- I need to care for an ill relative
- Not able to work or farm due to lack of inputs
- It is not the farming season
- I'm a student
- I'm pregnant or on maternity
- I am unable to work due to a disability
- I am retired or I am too old
- Other

41 Currently, what are your main sources of income? (maximum 3)

❗ Check all that apply

❗ Please select at most 3 answers

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Paid work
- Self-employed/ have my own business (example: hairdresser or sex worker)
- I am a daily wage earner (example: domestic workers)
- Petty trade
- From agriculture
- I am in survival mode (example: recycling and selling in slums, begging)
- Money sent by family members (inside or outside of South Africa)
- Assistance from the Government (social grants or the COVID-19 grant)
- Assistance from NGOs / charitable organisation
- Pension for me or a family member
- Transactional sex or I have a sugar daddy
- I do not have any source of income

Other:

Select the bigger source of income. If needed you may chose a maximum of 3 sources of income

42 Did your total income change since COVID-19 started?

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Increased
- No change
- Decreased

a3

a2

a1

43 How much has your income been reduced due to the COVID-19 crisis?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Decreased' at question '42 [Q42]' (Did your total income change since COVID-19 started?)

📌 Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- No change in my income
- reduced by less than half my income
- reduced by about half my income
- reduced by more than half my income
- I lost all my income

44 How are you coping with this reduction in your income?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Decreased' at question '42 [Q42]' (Did your total income change since COVID-19 started?)

📌 Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Relied on savings
- Reduced food consumption
- Reduced non-food consumption
- Did nothing
- Transactional sex or Sex work
- Received assistance
- Help from family
- Sale of assets

Other:

45 Do you access special COVID-19 relief grant or other COVID-19 support measures (example: social grants or food vouchers)

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes I applied, and I received these support measures
- Yes I applied, and I am waiting for the support measure
- I can access these support measures if I want, but I don't
- I have been denied access
- These measures are not applicable to me
- I did not know there was special relief measure for me
- I cannot or do not wish to answer this question

46 Since the COVID-19 crisis began, do you eat less or skip meals because there was not enough money for food?

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

47 Do you have enough money today to cover the daily expenses of today and tomorrow?

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

48 Do you have a bank account in your name?

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

Yes

No

49

Do you currently participate in a stokvel or other cooperative?

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

Yes

No

50 In the past 6 months, did you not pay or underpay your rent or bond?

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

Yes

No

I cannot or do not wish to answer this question

Does not apply to me

51 Since the COVID-19 crisis began, did you move in with other people, even for a little while, because of financial problems?

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No
- I cannot or do not wish to answer this question

52 How many times did you have to move since COVID-19 crisis began?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '51 [Q51]' (Since the COVID-19 crisis began, did you move in with other people, even for a little while, because of financial problems?)

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- 0
- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- more than 5
-

53

Think of a ladder representing where people stand in your country.

At the top of the ladder are the people who are the best off.
At the bottom are the people who are the worst off.

Where would you place yourself on this ladder at this moment?

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- 10, among those having most money, most education and most respected jobs
- 9
- 8
- 7
- 6
- 5
- 4
- 3
- 2
- 1, among those having the least money, least education and least respected jobs or no job

54

Now, think of a ladder representing where people stand in your local community.

Where would you place yourself on this ladder at this moment?

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- 10, highest standing in my community
- 9
- 8
- 7
- 6
- 5
- 4
- 3
- 2
- 1, lowest standing in my community

Behavioural economics

This section is on how you make your choices and your decisions, how you decide on courses of action.

55 How willing are you to take risks, in general?

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- 10, very willing
- 9
- 8
- 7
- 6
- 5
- 4
- 3
- 2
- 1
- 0, very unwilling

56 How willing are you to give to good causes without expecting anything in return?

📌 Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- 10, very willing to do so
- 9
- 8
- 7
- 6
- 5
- 4
- 3
- 2
- 1
- 0, very unwilling to do so

57

Imagine the following situation: Today you unexpectedly received 2,200 RAND. How much of this amount would you donate to a good cause?

📌 Only numbers may be entered in this field.

📌 Your answer must be between 0 and 20000

Please write your answer here:

58 How willing are you to give up something that is beneficial for you today in order to benefit more from that in the future?

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- 10, very willing to do so
- 9
- 8
- 7
- 6
- 5
- 4
- 3
- 2
- 1
- 0, very unwilling to do so

59 How well does the following statement describe you as a person: “I only act to satisfy immediate concerns, figuring that I will take care of future problems that may occur at a later date”

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- 5, it describes me perfectly
- 4, it somewhat describes me
- 3, uncertain
- 2, it somewhat does not describe me
- 1, it does not describe me at all

60 How well does the following statement describe you as a person: “I assume that people have only the best intentions”

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- 10, describes me perfectly
- 9
- 8
- 7
- 6
- 5
- 4
- 3
- 2
- 1
- 0, does not describe me at all

Your health and wellbeing

This section contains questions on health and non-health impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic.

Remember, your answers are confidential and you may skip a question if you are not comfortable with it.

61 Imagine a ladder with steps representing happiness in life, with the 10th step being the happiest. On which step of the ladder do you stand at this time?

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- 10, the best possible life for me
- 9
- 8
- 7
- 6
- 5
- 4
- 3
- 2
- 1
- 0, the worst possible life for me

62 Over the past 2 weeks, how often have you been bothered by the following problems?

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Nearly every day (12-14 days)	More than half the days (8-11 days)	Several days (1-7 days)	Not at all (0 day)
Feeling down, depressed or hopeless	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Little interest or pleasure in doing things	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Feeling nervous, anxious or on edge	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Not being able to stop or control worrying	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

63 In the past 6 months, how often have you thought about taking your own life?

① Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Never
- Seldom
- Very often
- All the time

64

If you're thinking about suicide, be sure to talk to other people about it. They can be friends or family members, but they don't have to be. It can be difficult to talk about this topic with people close to you. What is important is that you talk to someone.

You can do this by phone, chat, e-mail or in person:

South African Depression and Anxiety Group (sadag.org)
(<https://www.sadag.org/>)

Or call (toll free): 0800 567 567

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Seldom' or 'All the time' or 'Very often' at question '63 [Q63]' (In the past 6 months, how often have you thought about taking your own life?)

65 Which of the following healthcare services did you access in the last year?

🗖️ Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Public Healthcare (clinic, hospital)
- Private Healthcare (clinic, hospital, pharmacy)
- Traditional healer
- None, I don't want to use any healthcare services
- I cannot afford any healthcare

Other:

66

Did the COVID-19 pandemic have an impact on your attendance at the health facilities for the following services when you needed them?

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Yes	No	Not needed
HIV services	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Tuberculosis services	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Family planning	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Safe abortion care	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Sexually transmitted infection (STI)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Services for gender-based violence or intimate partner violence	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Gender-affirming hormone therapy	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other chronic care (diabetes, hypertension, cardiovascular disease)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

67 Are there costs which are preventing you from accessing the HIV or health services you needed above?

🗳️ Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Transportation cost
- The cost of medicines or tests
- Fees at the clinic or hospital
- The additional nonofficial fees (example baksheesh)
- The income I would miss out on while going to access these health services
- I have no money or all the money I have is being used for food and essential items
- I prefer not to answer
- None, I have no financial issues to access healthcare services
- Other:

68 Are there other reasons that prevent you from accessing family planning, or the HIV services you needed above?

❗ Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- The road to the health facility is risky for me (e.g. violence, high risk of sexual assault)
- I'm worried people could discover my sexual orientation
- I'm worried people could discover my HIV status
- Last time I went for HIV or health service I was humiliated
- Last time I went for HIV or health service I faced improper treatment (violence, insult, or discrimination)
- I do not have time to go to the health facility
- The service was offered at school or at a local NGO and it is now closed due to COVID-19
- I am not ready to deal with my HIV infection
- I fear being infected with COVID-19 in the health facility
- I prefer not to answer
- Other:

69 Did you become pregnant during the COVID-19 pandemic?

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No
- I don't know
- I cannot or do not wish to answer

70 Was this pregnancy planned?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '69 [Q69]' (Did you become pregnant during the COVID-19 pandemic?)

🗨️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No
- No, I was raped
- I don't know
- I cannot or do not wish to answer this question

71

If you are a survivor of rape, we encourage you to report the incident to the nearest police station and health facility.

Please do not hesitate to reach out for assistance. Take note or take a screenshot of these numbers:

Rape Crisis 24 Hour Crisis line: 033 395 4327

Stop Gender Violence Helpline: 0800 150 150

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No, I was raped' at question '70 [Q70]' (Was this pregnancy planned?)

72 Have you attended antenatal care during this pregnancy?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '69 [Q69]' (Did you become pregnant during the COVID-19 pandemic?)

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No
- I don't know
- I cannot or do not wish to answer

73 Where did/do you plan on delivering your baby?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '69 [Q69]' (Did you become pregnant during the COVID-19 pandemic?)

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Health facility
- Home with assistance of community health worker
- Home, non-assisted
- I don't know

74 When was your last HIV test? *

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- In the last 3 months
- 4 to 6 months ago
- 7 to 12 months ago
- More than 12 months ago
- I never had an HIV test

75 Do you know your HIV status?* *

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- I am HIV-positive
- I am HIV-negative
- I don't know
- I cannot or do not wish to answer

76 Are you currently taking HIV (antiretroviral) treatment?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'I am HIV-positive' at question '75 [Q75]' (Do you know your HIV status?*)

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

77 Is there a reason you are not taking HIV antiretroviral therapy?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No' at question '76 [Q76]' (Are you currently taking HIV (antiretroviral) treatment?)

🚫 Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- I used to, but stopped since COVID-19 crisis started
- Medication is currently not available at the clinic or hospital
- I am unable to collect medications at the clinic or hospital
- I cannot tolerate medication side effects or am worried about taking the pills
- I do not feel treatment is needed
- I am worried someone would find out my HIV status
- I am not ready to deal with my HIV infection
- I am worried the healthcare workers would treat me badly or disclose my HIV status without my consent
- I do not qualify for treatment because my CD4s are too high
- I am not sure I can access it as migrant or refugee
- No, for other reasons

78 Since COVID-19 crisis started, did you have an HIV viral load or CD4 test?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'I am HIV-positive' at question '75 [Q75]' (Do you know your HIV status?*)

🚫 Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

79 What are the reasons you could not have an HIV viral load or CD4 test in the last 12 months?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No' or 'I don't know' at question '78 [Q78]' (Since COVID-19 crisis started, did you have an HIV viral load or CD4 test?)

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- It was planned and cancelled because of COVID-19
- I cannot afford the costs of the test
- I did not follow up with my lab test
- I was not aware I should do regular HIV viral load test every year
- I am not sure I can do HIV viral load test here as migrant or refugee
- I don't know what "viral load" and "CD4 test" mean

Gender-based violence

Since COVID-19 crisis started, many girls and women have been facing increased violence. This violence can be physical or sexual, but it can also be emotional and financial.

This section poses sensitive questions. You may skip any question you are not comfortable answering.

80 Do you feel that you are currently experiencing:

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- More violence than before the COVID-19 crisis
- The same level of violence as before the COVID-19 crisis
- Less violence than before the COVID-19 crisis
- I am not experiencing any violence
- I cannot or do not wish to answer this question

81 From whom are you experiencing violence?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Less violence than before the COVID-19 crisis' or 'The same level of violence as before the COVID-19 crisis' or 'More violence than before the COVID-19 crisis' at question '80 [Q80]' (Do you feel that you are currently experiencing:)

🚫 Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Family
- Romantic / Sexual partner
- Friends
- Neighbours
- Healthcare providers
- Police and/or military
- Employer or co-workers
- Religious or faith community
- Teachers or school
- Government representatives
- Reporters and the media
- Other

82 Since COVID-19 crisis began, how often did your partner, husband or parent try to keep you from going to work or school?

🚫 Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Very often
- Often
- Sometimes
- Rarely
- Never

83 Since the COVID-19 crisis began, how often did your partner, husband or parent withhold money, make you ask for money, or take your money?

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Very often
- Often
- Sometimes
- Rarely
- Never

84 Since COVID-19 crisis began, how often did your partner, husband or parent try to keep you from seeing friends and family?

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Very often
- Often
- Sometimes
- Rarely
- Never

85 Since COVID-19 crisis began, how often did your partner, husband or parent try to insult and criticize you?

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Very often
- Often
- Sometimes
- Rarely
- Never

86 Since the COVID-19 crisis began, has your partner/s or husband slapped, punched, kicked, or shoved you?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Less violence than before the COVID-19 crisis' or 'The same level of violence as before the COVID-19 crisis' or 'More violence than before the COVID-19 crisis' at question '80 [Q80]' (Do you feel that you are currently experiencing:)

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No
- I cannot or do not wish to answer this question

87 If yes, did this happen...

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '86 [Q86]' (Since the COVID-19 crisis began, has your partner/s or husband slapped, punched, kicked, or shoved you?)

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Before the COVID-19 crisis
- Since the COVID-19 crisis started
- Both before and after the COVID-19 crisis

88 How often did this happen since the COVID-19 crisis began?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '86 [Q86]' (Since the COVID-19 crisis began, has your partner/s or husband slapped, punched, kicked, or shoved you?)

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Once
- 2 to 5 times
- 6 to 10 times
- 10 or more times
- I cannot or do not wish to answer this question

89 Since COVID-19 crisis began, has your partner or husband physically forced you to have sexual intercourse or do something sexual when you did not want to?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Less violence than before the COVID-19 crisis' or 'The same level of violence as before the COVID-19 crisis' or 'More violence than before the COVID-19 crisis' at question '80 [Q80]' (Do you feel that you are currently experiencing:)

📌 Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No
- I cannot or do not wish to answer this question

90 If yes, did this happen...

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '89 [Q89]' (Since COVID-19 crisis began, has your partner or husband physically forced you to have sexual intercourse or do something sexual when you did not want to?)

📌 Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Before the COVID-19 crisis
- Since the COVID-19 crisis started
- Both before and after the COVID-19 crisis

91 How often did this happen since the COVID-19 crisis began?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '89 [Q89]' (Since COVID-19 crisis began, has your partner or husband physically forced you to have sexual intercourse or do something sexual when you did not want to?)

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Once
- 2 to 5 times
- 6 to 10 times
- 10 or more times
- I cannot or do not wish to answer this question

92 Since COVID-19 crisis began, has someone who is **not** your regular partner forced or pressured you into sexual activity?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Less violence than before the COVID-19 crisis' or 'The same level of violence as before the COVID-19 crisis' or 'More violence than before the COVID-19 crisis' at question '80 [Q80]' (Do you feel that you are currently experiencing:)

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No
- I cannot or do not wish to answer this question

93 If yes, did this happen...

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '92 [Q92]' (Since COVID-19 crisis began, has someone who is not your regular partner forced or pressured you into sexual activity?)

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Before the COVID-19 crisis
- Since the COVID-19 crisis started
- Both before and after the COVID-19 crisis

94 How often did this happen since the COVID-19 crisis began?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '92 [Q92]' (Since COVID-19 crisis began, has someone who is not your regular partner forced or pressured you into sexual activity?)

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Once
- 2 to 5 times
- 6 to 10 times
- 10 or more times
- I cannot or do not wish to answer this question

95 If yes, who forced or pressured you to have sex in past 6 months?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '92 [Q92]' (Since COVID-19 crisis began, has someone who is not your regular partner forced or pressured you into sexual activity?)

📌 Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- A non-relative who lives with you
- Uniformed officer (police, military, security officer)
- Trusted individual (teacher, classmate, friend, co-worker, neighbour, religious leader)
- Stranger
- Sex work client
- Family member (parent, sibling, relative)
- Other
- I cannot or do not wish to answer

Please be reassured, all responses are anonymous and confidential

96 Did you report these instances of violence?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Less violence than before the COVID-19 crisis' or 'The same level of violence as before the COVID-19 crisis' or 'More violence than before the COVID-19 crisis' at question '80 [Q80]' (Do you feel that you are currently experiencing:)

📌 Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

97 What prevented you from reporting these instances of violence?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No' at question '96 [Q96]' (Did you report these instances of violence?)

🗳️ Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- I could not report the case due to lockdown/ my movements were restricted
- I don't know how to report this
- I was afraid of reporting the case
- The police will do nothing/ there will be no justice
- I was embarrassed
- I could not go to report the case (I was hurt and unable to move)
- Other

98

Nothing justifies any form of violence to you, never!

Please note or take a screenshot of the numbers and links below:

- Rape Crisis 24 Hour Crisis Line : 033 395 4327
- Stop Gender Violence Helpline: 0800 150 150
- Safeline: 0800 035 553

If you have experienced any police brutality, we encourage you to get in touch with SWEAT (Sex Workers Education and Advocacy Taskforce): <https://www.sweat.org.za>

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Less violence than before the COVID-19 crisis' or 'The same level of violence as before the COVID-19 crisis' or 'More violence than before the COVID-19 crisis' at question '80 [Q80]' (Do you feel that you are currently experiencing:)

Citizenship

This section contains 4 questions on citizenship and migrancy status. We assure you that this information is confidential. It is NOT shared with any authority.

99

What is your nationality?

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- South Africa
- Other African country
- Other non-African country

100

Please be reassured, all your answers are confidential and anonymous. They will NOT be shared with any authority, never.

Would you say you are:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Other non-African country' or 'Other African country' at question '99 [Q99]'
(What is your nationality?)

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- I am a migrant
- I am a refugee
- I am seeking asylum
- I cannot or do not wish to answer
- I don't know

101 Are you a returning migrant or have you been displaced from your home place?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'South Africa' at question '99 [Q99]' (What is your nationality?)

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- No, I am not a returning migrant or a displaced person
- Yes, I am a returning migrant (I migrated to another country and came back here)
- Yes, I have been forced to move from my home place
- I don't know
- I cannot or do not wish to answer this question

Return migrant refers to a South African citizen who went abroad and has returned to his home country. There are two main forms of return migration: voluntary return and forced return.

102 What are the main reasons you left?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes, I have been forced to move from my home place' or 'Yes, I am a returning migrant (I migrated to another country and came back here)' at question '101 [Q101]' (Are you a returning migrant or have you been displaced from your home place?)

❗ Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Economic reasons (example: job, salary)
- Family considerations
- Drought
- Tribal conflicts
- Forced relocation
- Insecurity
- Violation of human rights
- Armed conflicts

Other:

103 Do you have citizenship, or a valid residence permit (e.g. a work permit) for South Africa?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Other African country' or 'Other non-African country' at question '99 [Q99]' (What is your nationality?)

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No
- Unsure
- I cannot or do not wish to answer

Transactional Sex and Sex Work

This section contains questions about non-marital sexual relationships in exchange for money, material support or other benefit.

Please be reassured again, your answers are confidential and will NOT be shared with anyone. You can skip any question you are not comfortable with.

104 In the past 12 months, did you enter into a sexual relationship with a man (NOT your husband) mainly in order to get things that you need, money, gifts, school fees, clothes, or other things that are important to you?

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes, before the COVID-19 crisis but not now
- Yes, before the COVID-19 crisis and currently
- Yes, since the COVID-19 crisis but not before
- No, I have never
- I am unsure
- I do not want to answer

105 The last time you had sexual intercourse with this person from previous question, was a condom used?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes, since the COVID-19 crisis but not before' or 'Yes, before the COVID-19 crisis and currently' or 'Yes, before the COVID-19 crisis but not now' at question '104 [Q104]' (In the past 12 months, did you enter into a sexual relationship with a man (NOT your husband) mainly in order to get things that you need, money, gifts, school fees, clothes, or other things that are important to you?)

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

106

Have you ever engaged in sex work (being paid to have sex)?

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes, before the COVID-19 crisis but not now
- Yes, before the COVID-19 crisis and currently
- Yes, since the COVID-19 crisis but not before
- No, I have never
- I am unsure
- I do not want to answer

107

Has the COVID-19 crisis influenced your engagement in sex work?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes, since the COVID-19 crisis but not before' or 'Yes, before the COVID-19 crisis and currently' or 'Yes, before the COVID-19 crisis but not now' at question '106 [Q106]' (Have you ever engaged in sex work (being paid to have sex)?)

❗ Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- I engage in more sex work
- I engage in sex work online
- I earn less money per customer
- I take more risks or do things beyond my comfort
- I engage in more condomless sex
- I have stopped sex work
- I engage in less sex work
- No

108 What is the main reason for engaging in more condomless sex?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was at question '107 [Q107]' (Has the COVID-19 crisis influenced your engagement in sex work?)

❗ Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Condom stockout
- Afraid to go to the pharmacy
- Lockdown and curfews make it harder to buy condoms
- No money to buy condoms
- Harder to negotiate condom use with clients

Other:

109 Has the COVID-19 crisis created additional police crackdowns on sex work where you live?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes, since the COVID-19 crisis but not before' or 'Yes, before the COVID-19 crisis and currently' or 'Yes, before the COVID-19 crisis but not now' at question '106 [Q106]' (Have you ever engaged in sex work (being paid to have sex)?)

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No
- Unsure
- I cannot or do not wish to answer

Alcohol and Substance Use

This section is about alcohol and substance or drug use, as well as the impact of COVID-19 on its consumption.

110 How has your alcohol use changed since the COVID-19 crisis began?

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- I started drinking during COVID-19 crisis (I was not drinking before)
- Increased
- No change
- Decreased
- Does not apply to me, I don't drink

This includes umqombothi and other local alcoholic beverages

111

How often do you have a drink containing alcohol?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'I started drinking during COVID-19 crisis (I was not drinking before)' or 'No change' or 'Increased' or 'Decreased' at question '110 [Q110]' (How has your alcohol use changed since the COVID-19 crisis began?)

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Never
- Monthly or less
- 2 to 4 times a month
- 2 to 3 times per week
- 4 or more times per week

This includes umqombothi and other local alcoholic beverages

112

How many drinks do you have on a typical day when you are drinking?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'I started drinking during COVID-19 crisis (I was not drinking before)' or 'Increased' or 'No change' or 'Decreased' at question '110 [Q110]' (How has your alcohol use changed since the COVID-19 crisis began?)

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- 1 or 2
- 3 or 4
- 5 or 6
- 7 to 9
- 10 or more

This includes umqombothi and other local alcoholic beverages

113 How often do you have six or more drinks on one occasion?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'I started drinking during COVID-19 crisis (I was not drinking before)' or 'Increased' or 'No change' or 'Decreased' at question '110 [Q110]' (How has your alcohol use changed since the COVID-19 crisis began?)

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Never
- Less than monthly
- Monthly
- Weekly
- Daily or almost daily

This includes umqombothi and other local alcoholic beverages

114 Since COVID-19 crisis began, have you used tobacco products?

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No
- I don't know
- I cannot or do not wish to answer

115 How has your tobacco use changed since the COVID-19 crisis began?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '114 [Q114]' (Since COVID-19 crisis began, have you used tobacco products?)

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- I started smoking during Covid-19 crisis (I was not smoking before)
- Increased
- No change
- Decreased
- I cannot or do not wish to answer this question

116 Since the COVID-19 crisis began, have you used any substance or drug?

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No
- I don't know
- I cannot or do not wish to answer

For example: marijuana, opioid, heroine, glue, whoonga, nyaope, speed, ecstasy, flakka, cocaine, codeine, tramadol, etc...

117 How are you using these substance or drugs?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '116 [Q116]' (Since the COVID-19 crisis began, have you used any substance or drug?)

🗨️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- I inject them (with syringe and needles)
- I don't inject them, meaning I smoke, snort or swallow them
- I use both ways, meaning injecting and non-injecting them
- I cannot or do not wish to answer

118 About the injecting drugs, how often do you inject these drugs?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'I use both ways, meaning injecting and non-injecting them' or 'I inject them (with syringe and needles)' at question '117 [Q117]' (How are you using these substance or drugs?)

🗨️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Everyday
- Once weekly
- Two or more times a week
- Once a month or less

119 How has your use of injectable drugs changed since the COVID-19 crisis began?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'I inject them (with syringe and needles)' or 'I use both ways, meaning injecting and non-injecting them' at question '117 [Q117]' (How are you using these substance or drugs?)

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- I started injecting drug during Covid-19 crisis (I was not injecting drug before)
- Increased
- No change
- Decreased
- I cannot or do not wish to answer this question

120 Does the COVID-19 crisis limit your access to the following?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'I use both ways, meaning injecting and non-injecting them' or 'I inject them (with syringe and needles)' at question '117 [Q117]' (How are you using these substance or drugs?)

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Yes	No	I don't use
Access to the drug or substance you inject?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Safe injection equipment (needle exchange)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Opioid harm reduction (opiate substitution)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

121 Since COVID-19 crisis started, did you share your injecting equipment (example sharing needles)?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'I use both ways, meaning injecting and non-injecting them' or 'I inject them (with syringe and needles)' at question '117 [Q117]' (How are you using these substance or drugs?)

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No
- I don't know
- I cannot or do not wish to answer this question

122 How has COVID-19 crisis changed your sharing of injecting equipment?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '121 [Q121]' (Since COVID-19 crisis started, did you share your injecting equipment (example sharing needles)?)

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- I started sharing my injecting equipment during COVID-19 (I was not sharing it before)
- Increased
- No change
- Decreased
- I cannot or do not wish to answer this question

123 Now about the substances or drugs you swallow, snort or smoke (NOT injecting), how often do you use these drugs?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'I use both ways, meaning injecting and non-injecting them' or 'I don't inject them, meaning I smoke, snort or swallow them' at question '117 [Q117]' (How are you using these substance or drugs?)

🗨️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Everyday
- Once weekly
- Two or more times a week
- Once a month or less
- I only used it once

124 How has your non-injecting drug use changed since the COVID-19 crisis began?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'I use both ways, meaning injecting and non-injecting them' or 'I don't inject them, meaning I smoke, snort or swallow them' at question '117 [Q117]' (How are you using these substance or drugs?)

🗨️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- I started using drug during Covid-19 crisis (I was not using drug before)
- Increased
- No change
- Decreased
- I cannot or do not wish to answer this question

HIV Stigma

If you live with HIV, you may face stigma. Let's talk about it

Choose how you feel about each statement. We understand some questions might sound disturbing. Please share your experience. It will help to create a more inclusive environment for everyone.

125 Some people avoid touching me once they know I have HIV

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'I am HIV-positive' at question '75 [Q75]' (Do you know your HIV status?*)

🗨️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree
- I don't know

126 People I care about stopped contacting me after learning I have HIV

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'I am HIV-positive' at question '75 [Q75]' (Do you know your HIV status?*)

🗨️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree
- I don't know

127 I have lost friends by telling them I have HIV

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

((Q75.NAOK (/admin/questions/sa/view/surveyid/364192/gid/896/qid/24852) == "A1"))

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree
- I don't know

128 Telling someone I have HIV is risky

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

((Q75.NAOK (/admin/questions/sa/view/surveyid/364192/gid/896/qid/24852) == "A1"))

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree
- I don't know

129 I work hard to keep my HIV a secret

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

((Q75.NAOK (/admin/questions/sa/view/surveyid/364192/gid/896/qid/24852) == "A1"))

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree
- I don't know

130

I am very careful whom I tell that I have HIV

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

((Q75.NAOK (/admin/questions/sa/view/surveyid/364192/gid/896/qid/24852) == "A1"))

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree
- I don't know

131 People with HIV are treated like outcasts

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

((Q75.NAOK (/admin/questions/sa/view/surveyid/364192/gid/896/qid/24852) == "A1"))

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree
- I don't know

132 Most people believe a person who has HIV is dirty

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

((Q75.NAOK (/admin/questions/sa/view/surveyid/364192/gid/896/qid/24852) == "A1"))

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree
- I don't know

133 Most people are uncomfortable around someone with HIV

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

((Q75.NAOK (/admin/questions/sa/view/surveyid/364192/gid/896/qid/24852) == "A1"))

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree
- I don't know

134 I feel guilty because I have HIV

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

((Q75.NAOK (/admin/questions/sa/view/surveyid/364192/gid/896/qid/24852) == "A1"))

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree
- I don't know

135 People's attitudes about HIV make me feel worse about myself

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

((Q75.NAOK (/admin/questions/sa/view/surveyid/364192/gid/896/qid/24852) == "A1"))

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree
- I don't know

136 I feel I'm not as good a person as others because I have HIV

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

((Q75.NAOK (/admin/questions/sa/view/surveyid/364192/gid/896/qid/24852) == "A1"))

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree
- I don't know

137 In the last 6 months, have you ever been excluded from social gatherings or activities (e.g., weddings, funerals, parties, clubs) because of your HIV status?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'I am HIV-positive' at question '75 [Q75]' (Do you know your HIV status?*)

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes, once
- Yes, several times
- No
- I don't know
- It doesn't apply to me

138 Living with HIV can open new horizons and positively affects us deep inside. Which of the following have been positively affected by your HIV status

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'I am HIV-positive' at question '75 [Q75]' (Do you know your HIV status?*)

❗ Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- My self-confidence
- My self-respect
- My ability to respect others
- My ability to cope with stress
- My ability to better take care of my health
- My ability to contribute to my community

Other:

Transgender people

This module is about your needs as a transgender person and how the COVID-19 crisis affected your access to services you need

139 In the past 3 months, has the COVID-19 situation limited your ability to access medications and hormones specific to your trans healthcare?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Transgender man (female to male)' or 'Transgender woman (male to female)' at question '22 [Q22]' (How would you primarily define your gender identity?)

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No
- I don't use this resource
- I don't know
- I cannot or do not wish to answer this question

140 In the past 3 months, has the COVID-19 situation limited your ability to access to non-medical supplies? (example: make-up, shaving supplies, wigs, breast forms, etc.)

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Transgender man (female to male)' or 'Transgender woman (male to female)' at question '22 [Q22]' (How would you primarily define your gender identity?)

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No
- I don't use this resource
- I don't know
- I cannot or do not wish to answer this question

141 In the past 3 months, has the COVID-19 situation limited your ability to access to therapy or counselling services for transgender-specific support? (including peer support groups)

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Transgender man (female to male)' or 'Transgender woman (male to female)' at question '22 [Q22]' (How would you primarily define your gender identity?)

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No
- I don't use this resource
- I don't know
- I cannot or do not wish to answer this question

142 In the past 3 months, has the COVID-19 situation limited your ability to access gender-affirmation or transition-related surgery?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Transgender man (female to male)' or 'Transgender woman (male to female)' at question '22 [Q22]' (How would you primarily define your gender identity?)

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No
- I don't use this resource
- I don't know
- I cannot or do not wish to answer this question

143

If yes, how was your surgery or surgeries impacted?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '142 [Q142]' (In the past 3 months, has the COVID-19 situation limited your ability to access gender-affirmation or transition-related surgery?)

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Cancelled without rescheduling and/or delayed indefinitely
- Rescheduled and completed
- Rescheduled for the future with the same provider
- Rescheduled for the future with a different provider

End

144

Thank you for completing our survey!

Would you like to give us permission to recontact you on this telephone number in the future for more information or to find out if you would be willing to participate in another survey?

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

145 Please be reassured, your contact will be permanently and irremediably disconnected from your answers

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '144 [Q144]' (Thank you for completing our survey! Would you like to give us permission to recontact you on this telephone number in the future for more information or to find out if you would be willing to participate in another survey?)

Thank you for your participation!

You can learn more about the survey here:

Submit your survey.

Thank you for completing this survey.

Appendix 2: Timeline

Research Activity	Location of Research Activity		Proposed Duration			
	Instit.*	Country	Start		End	
			Month	Year	Month	Year
Protocol developed		Nigeria, South Africa, Senegal, Egypt, Zimbabwe, Switzerland, France	Q3	2020	Q3	2020
Ethics committee approval		Nigeria, South Africa, Senegal, Egypt, Zimbabwe, WHO/UNAIDS	Q3	2020	Q3	2020
Survey instrument developed. (incl. translation & proofreading)		Nigeria, South Africa, Senegal, Egypt, Zimbabwe, Switzerland, France	Q3	2020	Q4	2020
Data collection		Nigeria, South Africa, Senegal, Egypt, Zimbabwe	Q4	2020	Q4	2020
Data analysis		Nigeria, South Africa, Senegal, Egypt, Zimbabwe, Switzerland, France	Q4	2020	Q2	2021
Preliminary report		Switzerland	Q4	2020	Q4	2020
Prepare and submit report for publication		Nigeria, South Africa, Senegal, Egypt, Zimbabwe, Switzerland, France	Q1	2021	Q2	2021
Disseminate findings for clinical and policy change		Nigeria, South Africa, Senegal, Egypt, Zimbabwe, Switzerland, France	Q1	2021	Q2	2021

* Institutions to be specified after the selection of partners

Appendix 3: Curriculum vitae

Appendix 4: Declaration of Confidentiality

DECLARATION OF CONFIDENTIALITY AND DATA PRIVACY

to be signed by all persons requesting the use of data from the surveys “Measuring the impact of COVID-19 crisis on well-being and economic vulnerability of young women and girls living with or at risk for HIV” in Nigeria and South Africa.

This document comprises two (2) pages

1. I will be bound by all the terms and conditions of the confidentiality undertaking signed by the duly designated representative of my research entity and will use the dataset indicated in the research proposal in accordance with the terms of use attached to the confidentiality undertaking.
2. I understand that I must treat all data related to the Survey ‘Measuring the impact of COVID-19 crisis on well-being and economic vulnerability of young women and girls living with or at risk for HIV’ in accordance with the EU Directive 95/46/EC and as amended, replaced or superseded from time to time, including by the EU General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 (GDPR)
3. I will:
 - a) use the dataset exclusively and solely for the specific study: _____
whose research objectives and aims are: _____
and research hypothesis(es) is(are): _____
for the following purposes (describe the type of product or publication): _____
the list of variables I want are the following: _____
 - b) safeguard the dataset and any usernames and passwords associated with it;
 - c) ensure that any results of analyses will not be disclosive or potentially disclosive in conjunction with other publicly available information;
 - d) acknowledge the dataset and its source in any research report or publication and also state that the results and conclusions are mine and not those of Caprisa, the Institute of Public Health of Obafemi Awolowo University, or UNAIDS;
 - e) provide Caprisa, the Institute of Public Health of Obafemi Awolowo University, and UNAIDS with references to publications and other research reports based on this dataset;
 - f) preserve the confidentiality of information pertaining to identifiable individuals, households and/or organisations, such as those using the email address provided in the survey to exercise their right of withdrawal;
 - g) submit the final complete output of my work for the confidentiality check to the competent staff from Caprisa, the Institute of Public Health of Obafemi Awolowo University, and UNAIDS (in case of access to secure use files);
 - h) destroy the dataset and any data or variables derived from it at the end of the research period specified in the research proposal and sign a declaration to the effect that it has been ensured that all data have been destroyed;
 - i) abide by any other conditions notified to me by Caprisa, the Institute of Public Health of Obafemi Awolowo University, and UNAIDS (e.g. guidelines for publication);
 - j) inform the Caprisa, the Institute of Public Health of Obafemi Awolowo University, and UNAIDS immediately about any breach of the confidentiality rules laid down in the confidentiality undertaking or in the terms of use of confidential data for scientific purposes.

4. I will not:
 - a) use the data for purposes other than the production described in 3.a above
 - b) use the data (scientific use files) outside the premises of my research entity;
 - c) allow non-authorized users to access the dataset (authorized users are named in the research proposal);
 - d) use the data for research purposes before it is checked for confidentiality by Caprisa, the Institute of Public Health of Obafemi Awolowo University, and UNAIDS (in case of access to secure use files)
 - e) remove the data or any part of it (in case of access to secure use files);
 - f) attempt to link the data to other (including public) datasets, whether or not provided by Caprisa, the Institute of Public Health of Obafemi Awolowo University, or UNAIDS, if not expressly agreed;
 - g) attempt to identify any individual record (individual, household, business, etc.) in the dataset or claim to have done so;
 - h) release or publish any information or results which identify any individual record or may lead to the identification of any individual record.
 - i) Publish any form of documents using these data in [predatory journals or publishers](#) (see, for example, <https://predatoryjournals.org/the-list> , and <https://beallslist.net/>).

5. I certify that I have read all of the above clauses, that I understand that I am accountable for the correct and responsible use of the data and data access system and that I understand that if I fail to comply with these clauses, my access to the dataset will be withdrawn and I will be liable to any other sanctions that may be determined by my research entity or are specified in the applicable civil or penal law.

Name:Signature:Date: